

DETERMINANTS OF BANTEN SHIPPING POLYTECHNIC CADET SATISFACTION

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Abstract

Cadet satisfaction at the Banten shipping polytechnic is the main thing due to the development of innovation from the Banten shipping polytechnic. This research uses motivation variables and innovative work behavior. During the pandemic, these educational institutions implemented online learning. At the Banten Shipping Polytechnic, innovation in learning is in line with government regulations which require online learning. Banten Shipping Polytechnic innovates in the online learning process.

Keywords: Work Motivation, Innovative Work Behavior, Cadet Satisfaction.

INTRODUCTION

In 2019, the Covid-19 pandemic occurred throughout the world, causing all sectors to experience the impact of the pandemic. All economic projections before the pandemic corrected themselves. In fact, projections of economic growth in several countries have had to be replaced by the reality of a recession. Painful and disappointing are words that accurately describe the conditions at that time, but we must accept it with grace, we accept it as part of the reality of life (Hasan Chabibie, 2021). The pandemic has been felt in various sectors, including the world of education. In various parts of the world, this global pandemic has had an impact on many dimensions, including economics, health, politics and international relations. In fact, the world of education also experienced a significant impact (Hasan Chabibie, 2020).

The Covid 19 pandemic has haunted the entire world, especially Indonesia since the beginning of 2020. What is COVID-19? COVID-19 is an abbreviation for coronavirus disease and is even referred to as the 2019 novel coronavirus or 2019-nCoV (U. Unicef, personal communication, 2020). The COVID-19 virus is related to Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome Coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV) which can also be fatal (Meng et al., 2019). The new virus can be transmitted in just a few minutes through droplets or even touching infected metal surfaces or other materials from people who have respiratory problems. Although the elderly and very young children are easily infected, no one is immune to this new infectious disease once it invades the body, so everyone is immune to its devastating effects.

The school environment is an area where many people gather and almost 90% of children to teenagers are ages that are very vulnerable to interaction and transmission and in order to prevent transmission from occurring, the government has adopted a policy of closing schools. As of 06 April 2020, UNESCO (2020) reported that there were 1,576,021,818 students affected out of 91.3% of students registered in 188 countries for all levels. A number of schools and universities have stopped teaching and learning activities (KBM) in class to prevent the spread

of the Corona virus (COVID-19). In order to reduce transmission, the Indonesian government requires educational institutions to implement online learning (Makarim, 2020). In the process there are several online applications that can be accessed by teachers and cadets to carry out learning from home.

Learning is something that is very important for children in order to prepare themselves for the future (Nilayani, 2020). Sooner or later every child will be required to become an independent person in the future by changing their behavior for the better. The Banten Shipping Polytechnic which operates in the education sector, which in fact has been using a face-to-face learning system in general plus deepening of the material through practice in the laboratory, has changed to online learning. Online learning has become a mainstream learning interaction model during the Covid-19 pandemic. Online distance learning is effective for handling learning that allows teachers and cadets to interact in virtual classes that can be accessed anywhere and anytime (Sadikin & Hamidah, 2020). One of the popular learning alternatives currently used is virtual classes using Microsoft Teams and YouTube videos. Learning using Microsoft Teams is very good for increasing cadets' interest in learning (Situmorang, 2020)

Banten Shipping Polytechnic is a vocational school that concentrates on producing graduates who are experts in the field of shipping. Cadet satisfaction and academic performance have become a major focus of scholars and policy makers in competitive learning environments (Weerasinghe & Fernando, 2018). (Barber, Mourshed, Company, Barber, & Mourshed, 2007), this is supported by the results of research conducted by Hattie which states that the competency of teaching staff (lecturers) is an important factor in determining the quality of education (Hattie, 2018), to continue to improve competence of teaching staff (lecturers) in several training programs implemented by the government through teaching programs (Barber et al., 2007) that are prepared to face future challenges that are closely related to the development of information technology. Cadet perception surveys are also considered the most common approach to inspect and improve campus quality. Thus, the vital role of factors such as educational programs, quality of academic personnel, service accessibility, training environment and university facilities in shaping cadet satisfaction and their academic performance is attracted and recognized in educational literature (Lee et al., 2020).

Higher education has changed over the past few years. Lecturers are not the center of the learning process or the only ones who have knowledge. Currently, Cadets are in the center, and lecturers use new methodologies to stimulate their creativity, teamwork, skills, and so on. In class, Cadets analyze, research and create all activities and practices that the lecturer has prepared beforehand, using active learning strategies. This new approach requires Cadets to think, act or reflect on what they learn (Martínez-Jiménez & Ruiz-Jiménez, 2020).

On average, current cadets are part of Generation Z (Gen Z) who were born between 1995 and 2015 and first entered higher education in 2013 (Seemiller & Grace, 2017). Current cadets who are Gen Z rely heavily on information technology and prefer to learn and work independently at their own pace (Seemiller & Grace, 2017). The newest generation really enjoys application-based learning, wants to address the root causes of social problems, and aspires to change the world. If Gen Z is loyal to their generational cohort, they will prefer entrepreneurial career

opportunities over commitment to an organization and place their own happiness and enjoyment of work as another consideration. Furthermore, anxiety is an important issue for Cadets

Education in the era of the Industrial Revolution 4.0 to describe various ways of integrating cyber technology both physically and non-physically in learning. The online campus learning system can be used with technological means to create a Smart Campus in the Banten Shipping Polytechnic area so that distance learning (PJJ) can be accessed anywhere, teachers are asked to be more creative and innovative (Yulianto, 2021).

Innovating and staying above the competition are adaptations that must be implemented by the Banten shipping polytechnic which must make learning a priority. Understanding new industry developments, product innovation, changes in customer needs and competitive threats are some of the issues that should rank high among organizational learning requirements. Even in situations with minimal competition, continuous learning is necessary for organizations to thrive and survive (Flanigan, 2016).

Transformational leaders are needed to face this situation. Transformational thinking and leadership style can have a big impact on all subordinates at work, and can help organizations continue to innovate to adapt to current developments. Transformational leadership behavior influences the adoption of generative thinking and the pursuit of organizational innovation. (Zuraik & Kelly, 2018).

In this research, it has been proven that transformational leadership can help influence organizations to continue to innovate, make organizational structures more effective, help motivate employees at work and help create the right organizational culture. In this way, the civilization of the Indonesian nation was formed which was able to actualize itself to grow and strengthen faith, piety and noble morals, including noble character and superior personality, as well as the exercise of taste to increase sensitivity and appreciation for the subtlety and beauty of art and culture, as well as the competence to express them.

Apart from that, employee self-confidence at work is an important thing at work. Self-efficacy is the foundation of lecturers' motivation at work (Cziraki et al., 2018). In order to realize the provision of access to education and culture based on information and communication technology, an Information and Communication Technology Development Plan (ICT Master Plan) is needed which is in line with the Strategic Plan of the Ministry of Transportation of the Republic of Indonesia as well as bureaucratic reform policies in increasing effectiveness and efficiency through process integration, sharing ICT resources and utilization determined by the Ministry of State Apparatus and Bureaucratic Reform.

The Covid-19 pandemic has become a momentum to motivate all elements to make changes in a short and short time in order to improvise an organization where currently competition between private universities is very high so that student satisfaction must be prioritized by universities. Attracting new students and retaining existing students has become a pressing and important goal for many existing higher education institutions (Angell et al., 2008). Universities must ultimately aim to gain a competitive advantage in the future and need to find

effective and creative ways to attract, maintain and foster closer relationships with students (Hasan et al., 2009)

Research Objective

The goal of this research is to determine whether and how mindfulness- based interventions reduce digital technology-related disruptions in the classrooms of students in Jordan and Saudi Arabia. The goal of this study is to provide empirical evidence on the effectiveness of mindfulness- based treatments in helping students reduce digital distractions, improve concentration, and become more actively involved in the learning process. To this end, studies will be conducted to determine how digital technology might help mitigate the negative effects of mindfulness practices. The purpose of the research is to establish the strength of the connection between the two factors. The research also hopes to unearth country-specific contextual factors that may influence the spread and success of mindfulness-based interventions in Jordan and Saudi Arabia. The investigation will include a comprehensive examination of both Jordan and Saudi Arabia.

METHODS

This research uses a quantitative approach, survey methods and path analysis techniques. This research was conducted at the Banten Shipping Polytechnic. The research was carried out from January 2021 to May 2021 and the population used in this research was cadets at the Banten Shipping Polytechnic, totaling 89 cadets, the sample in the research was part of the population. The sampling technique used is random sampling, namely a simple random sampling method.

The data collected used an instrument in the form of a questionnaire. The instrument was tested first before being used in research using validity and reliability tests and valid and invalid instrument items were obtained. These variables are as below:

a. Cadet Satisfaction

Cadet satisfaction is a student's subjective perception of how good the environmental conditions on campus are that can support the success of the studies they are currently undertaking with the following indicators: tangible, responsiveness, reliability, assurance, and empathy.

b. Work motivation

Work motivation is a person's psychological and physical encouragement in carrying out work leading to ability, behavior, initiative and responsibility with indicators: strength, initiative, intensity and perseverance.

c. Innovative work behavior

Innovative work behavior is everything that a person does in their work assignments with an orientation towards developing new ideas or concepts that can lead to progress, with indicators of developing ideas, applying creativity in work and making breakthroughs in implementing new ideas. Definisi Operasional

A. Data Analysis Techniques

The data analysis used for this research is descriptive analysis and inferential analysis. Descriptive analysis is used in terms of data presentation, central size, and spread size. Descriptive data analysis can be presented in the form of distribution tables and histograms. Central measures are the mean, median and mode. Measures of spread are variance and standard deviation. Inferential analysis is used to test hypotheses using path analysis which is preceded by normality tests, error estimates and regression analysis.

B. Statistical Hypothesis

A statistical hypothesis is a statement or conjecture about the condition of a population that is still temporary or has little truth. A statistical hypothesis can take the form of a variable such as binomial, Poisson, and normal or the value of a parameter, such as mean, variance, standard deviation, and proportion. Statistical hypotheses must be tested, because they must be in the form of quantities to be accepted or rejected. A statistical hypothesis will be accepted if the test results confirm the statement and will be rejected if the statement is refuted. In this research the statistical hypothesis proven is:

First hypothesis

H0: $\beta_1 \leq 0$, This means that there is no influence of work motivation (X1) on cadet satisfaction (Y).

H1: $\beta_1 > 0$, This means that there is an influence of work motivation (X1) on cadet satisfaction (Y).

Second hypothesis

H0: $\beta_2 \leq 0$, This means that there is no influence of innovative work behavior (X2) on cadet satisfaction (Y).

H1: $\beta_2 > 0$, This means that there is an influence of innovative work behavior (X2) on cadet satisfaction (Y).

a. Hipotesis ketiga

H0: $\beta_2 \leq 0$, This means that there is no influence of work motivation (X1) on innovative work behavior (X2).

H1: $\beta_2 > 0$, This means that there is an influence of work motivation (X1) on innovative work behavior (X2).

RESULTS

The data description in this section includes data on variable Y (Satisfaction) as an endogenous variable, variable X1 (Work Motivation) as an exogenous variable and variable X2 (Innovative Work Behavior) as an intermediate endogenous variable. The description of each variable is presented sequentially starting from variables Y, X1, and X2.

1. Satisfaction (Y)

From data obtained in the field which was then processed statistically into a frequency distribution list, the number of classes was calculated according to Sturges' rules, resulting in seven classes with a maximum score of 75 and a minimum score of 50, so the score range was 25. The results of the data calculation were obtained as an average. amounted to 67.89; standard deviation of 5.407; variance of 29.237; median of 69.00; and the mode is 75. The grouping of satisfaction data can be seen in the frequency distribution table as follows.

Table 4.1: Frequency Distribution of Satisfaction (Y)

		Interval Y			
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	50-53	1	1,1	1,1	1,1
	54-57	2	2,2	2,2	3,4
	58-61	8	9,0	9,0	12,4
	62-65	14	15,7	15,7	28,1
	66-69	28	31,5	31,5	59,6
	70-73	19	21,3	21,3	80,9
	74-77	17	19,1	19,1	100,0
	Total	89	100,0	100,0	

Based on the table above, a histogram will be created next. There are two axes needed to create a histogram, namely the vertical axis as the absolute frequency axis, and the horizontal axis as the satisfaction score axis. In this case, on the horizontal axis, the interval class boundaries are written, namely from 50 to 77. The histogram graph of the data distribution is shown in the following figure.

Picture 4.1: Satisfaction Data Histogram (Y)

2. Work motivation (X1)

Work motivation data has an empirical score range between 34 to 60, so the score range is 26. The results of data calculations obtained an average of 50.72; standard deviation of 5.553; variance of 30.841; median of 51.00; and the mode is 50. The grouping of work motivation data can be seen in the frequency distribution table as follows.

Table 4.2: Frequency Distribution of Work Motivation (X1)

		Interval X1			
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	34-37	2	2,2	2,2	2,2
	38-41	4	4,5	4,5	6,7
	42-45	8	9,0	9,0	15,7
	46-49	18	20,2	20,2	36,0
	50-53	29	32,6	32,6	68,5
	54-57	19	21,3	21,3	89,9
	58-61	9	10,1	10,1	100,0
Total		89	100,0	100,0	

Based on the table above, a histogram will be created next. There are two axes needed to create a histogram, namely the vertical axis as the absolute frequency axis, and the horizontal axis as the work motivation score axis. In this case, on the horizontal axis, the interval class boundaries are written, namely from 34 to 61. The histogram graph of the data distribution is shown in the following figure.

Picture 4.2: Work Motivation Data Histogram (X1)

3. Innovative Work Behavior (X2)

Innovative work behavior data has an empirical score range between 40 to 60, so the score range is 20. The results of data calculations obtained an average of 51.51; standard deviation of 5.369; variance of 28.821; median of 52.00; and the mode is 53. The grouping of innovative work behavior data can be seen in the frequency distribution table as follows.

Table 4.3: Frequency Distribution of Innovative Work Behavior (X2)

		Interval X2			
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	40-42	4	4,5	4,5	4,5
	43-45	10	11,2	11,2	15,7
	46-48	14	15,7	15,7	31,5
	49-51	15	16,9	16,9	48,3
	52-54	18	20,2	20,2	68,5
	55-57	15	16,9	16,9	85,4
	58-60	13	14,6	14,6	100,0
Total		89	100,0	100,0	

Based on the table above, a histogram will be created next. There are two axes needed to create a histogram, namely the vertical axis as the absolute frequency axis, and the horizontal axis as the innovative work behavior score axis. In this case, on the horizontal axis, the interval class boundaries are written, namely from 40 to 60. The histogram graph of the data distribution is shown in the following figure.

Picture 4.3: Histogram of Innovative Work Behavior Data (X2)

The recapitulation of the results of descriptive statistical calculations can be summarized in the following table.

Table 4.4: Summary of Descriptive Statistics

		Statistics		
		Kepuasan (Y)	Motivasi Kerja (X1)	Perilaku Kerja Inovatif (X2)
N	Valid	89	89	89
	Missing	0	0	0
Mean		67,89	50,72	51,51
Std. Error of Mean		,573	,589	,569
Median		69,00	51,00	52,00
Mode		75	50 ^a	53
Std. Deviation		5,407	5,553	5,369
Variance		29,237	30,841	28,821
Range		25	26	20
Minimum		50	34	40
Maximum		75	60	60
Sum		6042	4514	4584
a. Multiple modes exist. The smallest value is shown				

A) Testing Requirements Analysis

The requirement for path analysis is that the estimates between exogenous variables and endogenous variables are linear, thus the requirements that apply to regression analysis also automatically apply to the requirements for path analysis. The requirements that must be met in path analysis are that the research sample comes from a normally distributed population, the regression equation must be meaningful and linear, and the relationship between the variables in the model must be significant. In this regard, before testing the model, a test is first carried out on the requirements that apply in the path analysis.

1) Simple Regression Equation

a) Y atas X1

From the calculation data for preparing the regression equation model between work motivation and satisfaction in Appendix 6, the regression constant $a = 35.871$ and the regression coefficient $b = 0.631$ are obtained. Thus the relationship between the simple regression equation model is $\hat{Y} = 35.871 + 0.631X_1$.

b) Y atas X2

From the calculation data for preparing the regression equation model between innovative work behavior and satisfaction in Appendix 6, the regression constant $a = 31.536$ and the regression coefficient $b = 0.706$ are obtained. Thus the relationship between the simple regression equation model is $\hat{Y} = 31.536 + 0.706X_2$.

c) X2 atas X1

From the calculation data for preparing the regression equation model between work motivation and innovative work behavior in Appendix 6, the regression constant $a = 19.668$ and the regression coefficient $b = 0.628$ are obtained. Thus the relationship between the simple regression equation model is $= 19.668 + 0.628X_1$.

2) Normality Test

The data used in constructing the regression model must meet the assumption that the data comes from a normally distributed population. The normality assumption basically states that a regression model must have a normal distribution. The assumption test in this research was carried out by testing the normality of the data from the three research regression estimation errors to be analyzed. The normality test uses the SPSS program to determine whether the regression of Y on X is normally distributed or not, the results of which can be seen in the Kolmogorov Smirnov (Sig.) column.

Table 4.5: Regression Estimated Error Normality Test Results

Tests of Normality						
	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
Y Atas X1	,058	89	,200*	,988	89	,604
Y Atas X2	,069	89	,200*	,990	89	,729
X2 Atas X1	,073	89	,200*	,987	89	,511
*. This is a lower bound of the true significance.						
a. Lilliefors Significance Correction						

The table above shows that the probability value (Sig.) of all regression estimate errors is 0.200. The probability value is greater than the significance level (α) of 0.05, so all regression estimate error data is normally distributed

3) Significance Test and Regression Linearity

Before using the regression equation to draw conclusions in hypothesis testing, the regression model obtained was tested for significance and linearity using the F test with SPSS. The criteria for testing the significance and linearity of the regression model are set as follows:

Significant regression : $F_{hitung} > F_{tabel}$ on the Regression line

Linear regression : $F_{hitung} < F_{tabel}$ on the Deviation from line

Linearity.

a. Test of Significance and Linearity of Regression of Satisfaction on Work Motivation

Table 4.6: Test the Significance of Regression Y on X₁

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	1081,447	1	1081,447	63,084	,000 ^b
	Residual	1491,429	87	17,143		
	Total	2572,876	88			
a. Dependent Variable: Kepuasan (Y)						
b. Predictors: (Constant), Motivasi Kerja (X1)						

F distribution table using db numerator = 1 and db denominator (n - 2) = 87 with a significance level of 0.05. Obtained F_{tabel} of 3.95 and F_{count} of 63.084. This shows that $F_{count} > F_{tabel}$ and the probability value Sig. (0.000) < significant level (0.05), then the regression equation Y

on X1 is declared significant. The linearity test was carried out to test whether the two variables had a linear influence or not, the results of which can be seen in the following table.

Table 4.7: Regression Linearity Test Y on X

ANOVA Table							
			Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Kepuasan (Y) * Motivasi Kerja (X1)	Between Groups	(Combined)	1569,877	23	68,256	4,423	,000
		Linearity	1081,447	1	1081,447	70,084	,000
		Deviation from Linearity	488,430	22	22,201	1,439	,131
	Within Groups		1003,000	65	15,431		
	Total		2572,876	88			

F distribution table using numerator db = 22 and denominator db = 65 with a significance level of 0.05. Obtained Ftable of 1.71 and Fcount of 1.439. This shows that Fcount < Ftable and the probability value Sig. deviation from linearity (0.131) > significant level (0.05), then the estimated distribution of points forming a linear line is acceptable.

b. Test of Significance and Linearity of Regression of Satisfaction on Innovative Work Behavior

Table 4.8

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	1263,403	1	1263,403	83,939	,000 ^b
	Residual	1309,474	87	15,051		
	Total	2572,876	88			
a. Dependent Variable: Kepuasan (Y)						
b. Predictors: (Constant), Perilaku Kerja Inovatif (X2)						

F distribution table using db numerator = 1 and db denominator (n - 2) = 87 with a significance level of 0.05. Obtained Ftable of 3.95 and Fcount of 83.939. This shows that Fcount > Ftable and the probability value Sig. (0.000) < significant level (0.05), then the regression equation Y on X2 is declared significant. The linearity test was carried out to test whether the two variables had a linear influence or not, the results of which can be seen in the following table.

Table 4.9: Regression Linearity Test Y on X2

ANOVA Table							
			Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Kepuasan (Y) * Perilaku Kerja Inovatif (X2)	Between Groups	(Combined)	1688,451	20	84,423	6,491	,000
		Linearity	1263,403	1	1263,403	97,138	,000
		Deviation from Linearity	425,048	19	22,371	1,720	,054
	Within Groups		884,426	68	13,006		
	Total		2572,876	88			

F distribution table using numerator db = 19 and denominator db = 68 with a significance level of 0.05. Obtained Ftable of 1.74 and Fcount of 1.720. This shows that Fcount < Ftable and the

probability value Sig. deviation from linearity (0.054) > significant level (0.05), then the estimated distribution of points forming a linear line is acceptable.

c. Test of Significance and Linearity of Regression of Innovative Work Behavior on Work Motivation

Table 4.10: Test the Significance of Regression X₂ on X₁

ANOVA ^a						
	Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	1069,423	1	1069,423	63,429	,000 ^b
	Residual	1466,824	87	16,860		
	Total	2536,247	88			
a. Dependent Variable: Perilaku Kerja Inovatif (X ₂)						
b. Predictors: (Constant), Motivasi Kerja (X ₁)						

F distribution table using db numerator = 1 and db denominator (n - 2) = 87 with a significance level of 0.05. Obtained Ftable of 3.95 and Fcount of 63.429. This shows that Fcount > Ftable and the probability value Sig. (0.000) < significant level (0.05), then the regression equation X₂ on X₁ is declared significant. The linearity test was carried out to test whether the two variables had a linear influence or not, the results of which can be seen in the following table.

Table 4.11: Regression Linearity Test X₂ on X₁

ANOVA Table							
			Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Perilaku Kerja Inovatif (X ₂) *	Between Groups	(Combined)	1439,401	23	62,583	3,709	,000
		Linearity	1069,423	1	1069,423	63,375	,000
		Deviation from Linearity	369,977	22	16,817	,997	,481
Motivasi Kerja (X ₁)	Within Groups		1096,847	65	16,875		
	Total		2536,247	88			

F distribution table using numerator db = 22 and denominator db = 65 with a significance level of 0.05. Obtained Ftable of 1.71 and Fcount of 0.997. This shows that Fcount < Ftable and the probability value Sig. deviation from linearity (0.481) > significant level (0.05), then the estimated distribution of points forming a linear line is acceptable.

Table 4.12: Results of Significance Test and Regression Linearity Test

Reg	Persamaan	Uji Regresi		Uji Linearitas		Kesimpulan
		F _{hitung}	F _{tabel} α = 0,01	F _{hitung}	F _{tabel} α = 0,05	
Y atas X ₁	$\hat{Y} = 35,781 + 0,631X_1$	63,084	3,95	1,439	1,71	Regresi signifikan dan Regresi linear
Y atas X ₂	$\hat{Y} = 31,536 + 0,706X_2$	83,939	3,95	1,720	1,74	Regresi signifikan dan Regresi linear
X ₂ atas X ₁	$\hat{X}_2 = 19,668 + 0,628X_1$	63,429	3,95	0,997	1,71	Regresi signifikan dan Regresi linear

1) Model Testing

Picture 4.4: Structural Relationship Model between Variables

Based on Figure 4.4, there is a division into two models, namely the first model sub-structure and the second model sub-structure. It can be explained that the path coefficient value in the first model sub-structure is the path that connects the work motivation variable to the satisfaction variable, and the path that connects the innovative work behavior variable to the variable satisfaction. The path coefficient value in the second model substructure is the path that connects the work motivation variable to the innovative work behavior variable.

1. Calculation of Correlation Coefficient

Before calculations are carried out to test the causality model using the path analysis method, the research data is first tested and meets all the necessary requirements. One of the very important requirements that must be met is the existence of a significant correlation between related variables and their relationship to one another. From the results of the analytical calculations in Appendix 7, it can be summarized as follows:

Table 4.13: Summary of Correlation Coefficient Test Results

Correlations				
		Kepuasan (Y)	Motivasi Kerja (X1)	Perilaku Kerja Inovatif (X2)
Kepuasan (Y)	Pearson Correlation	1	,648**	,701**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		,000	,000
	N	89	89	89
Motivasi Kerja (X1)	Pearson Correlation	,648**	1	,649**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	,000		,000
	N	89	89	89
Perilaku Kerja Inovatif (X2)	Pearson Correlation	,701**	,649**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	,000	,000	
	N	89	89	89

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 4.13 shows that the probability value Sig. (2-tailed) all correlation coefficients are smaller than the significance level (α) of 0.05, so all correlation coefficients are declared significant.

2. Path Coefficients in the First Model Substructure

The structural equation formed in the first sub-structure model consists of 2 path coefficients from variables X1 to Y and X2 to Y in the form: $Y = \beta_{y1}X_1 + \beta_{y2}X_2 + \beta_{y\epsilon_1}$. Multiple correlation coefficient $R_{y.12} = 0.745$ with probability value $\text{Sig. } (0.000) < \text{significant level } (0.05)$, then the multiple correlation coefficient is declared significant. The coefficient of determination is $(R_{y.12})^2 = 0.556$ and the remainder ($\beta_{y\epsilon_1}$) is 0.444 which is influenced by other factors not studied such as leadership, reward, punishment, etc. So the form of the structural equation in the first sub structure model: $Y = 0.334X_1 + 0.484X_2 + 0.444$. A description of the estimated path coefficients for the first model is explained in table 4.14 and visualized in figure 4.5 below:

Table 4.14: First SPSS Model Results

Model		Coefficients ^a			t	Sig.
		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	26,289	4,032		6,520	,000
	Motivasi Kerja (X1)	,325	,092	,334	3,536	,001
	Perilaku Kerja Inovatif (X2)	,487	,095	,484	5,118	,000

a. Dependent Variable: Kepuasan (Y)

Picture 4.5 Empirical Path Diagram of Structural Model 1

3. Path Coefficients in the Second Model Substructure

The structural equation formed in the second sub-structure model formed by the path coefficient from variables X1 to X2 is in the form: $X_2 = \beta_{21}X_1 + \beta_{2\epsilon_2}$. Correlation coefficient $r_{12} = 0.649$ with probability value $\text{Sig. } (0.000) < \text{significant level } (0.05)$, then the correlation coefficient is declared significant. The coefficient of determination is $(r_{12})^2 = 0.422$ and the remainder ($\beta_{2\epsilon_2}$) is 0.578 which is influenced by other factors not studied such as work environment, organizational climate, etc. So the form of the structural equation in the second sub-structure model: $X_2 = 0.649X_1 + 0.578$. A description of the estimated path coefficients for the second model is explained in table 4.15 and visualized in figure 4.6 below:

Table 4.15: Second SPSS Model Results

Model		Coefficients ^a				
		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
2	(Constant)	19,668	4,021		4,891	,000
	Motivasi Kerja (X1)	,628	,079	,649	7,964	,000

a. Dependent Variable: Perilaku Kerja Inovatif (X2)

Picture 4.6 Empirical Path Diagram of Structural Model 2

2) Pengujian Hipotesis

1. First Hypothesis

Work motivation has a direct positive effect on satisfaction.

$$H_0: \beta_{y1} < 0$$

$$H_1: \beta_{y1} > 0$$

H0 is rejected if $t_{count} > t_{table}$.

From the results of path analysis calculations, the direct influence of work motivation on satisfaction, the path coefficient value is 0.334 and the tcount value is 3.536. Because the tcount coefficient value is greater than the ttable value at $dk = 86$ for $\alpha = 0.05$ of 1.99 and the probability value Sig. (0.001) < significant level (0.05), then H0 is rejected and H1 is accepted, thus work motivation has a direct positive effect on satisfaction which is acceptable and can provide findings that work motivation has a direct positive effect on satisfaction so it can be concluded that satisfaction is influenced directly positive by work motivation.

2. Second Hypothesis

Innovative work behavior has a direct positive effect on satisfaction.

$$H_0: \beta_{y2} < 0$$

H1: $\beta_2 > 0$

H0 is rejected if $t_{count} > t_{table}$.

From the results of path analysis calculations, the direct influence of innovative work behavior on satisfaction, the path coefficient value is 0.484 and the t-count value is 5.118. Because the tcount coefficient value is greater than the ttable value at $dk = 86$ for $\alpha = 0.05$ of 1.99 and the probability value Sig. (0.000) < significant level (0.05), then H0 is rejected and H1 is accepted, thus innovative work behavior has a direct positive effect on satisfaction and can be accepted. This hypothesis produces findings that innovative work behavior has a direct positive effect on satisfaction and it can be concluded that satisfaction is directly positively influenced by innovative work behavior.

3. Third Hypothesis

Work motivation has a direct positive effect on innovative work behavior.

H0: $\beta_{21} < 0$

H1: $\beta_{21} > 0$

H0 is rejected if $t_{count} > t_{table}$.

From the results of path analysis calculations, the direct influence of work motivation on innovative work behavior, the path coefficient value is 0.649 and the t-count value is 7.964. Because the tcount coefficient value is greater than the ttable value at $dk = 87$ for $\alpha = 0.05$ of 1.99 and the probability value Sig. (0.000) < significant level (0.05), then H0 is rejected and H1 is accepted, thus work motivation has a direct positive effect on innovative work behavior which can be accepted. The results of this hypothesis provide findings that work motivation has a direct positive effect on innovative work behavior. It was concluded that innovative work behavior was directly positively influenced by work motivation.

DISCUSSION

1. The Influence of Work Motivation on Satisfaction

From the results of testing the first hypothesis, it can be concluded that there is a positive direct influence of work motivation on satisfaction with a path coefficient value of 0.334. This means that work motivation has a direct positive effect on satisfaction. The results of this research are in line with the opinions of several experts, including Humphreys and Einstein, explaining that a comprehensive work motivation model must include elements of personality, business aspects, abilities, expectations, capabilities, valence, goal-directed behavior, intrinsic and extrinsic rewards for lecturers (Ulrich, 2008:4).

Lecturers' work motivation at work is reflected in every activity at work which has an impact on the satisfaction of cadets as customers. Work motivation represents a psychological process that gives rise to the desire to develop, direct and continuously maintain voluntary actions directed by the leader.

Work motivation is really needed by every lecturer in carrying out their duties, this is very closely related to the performance they will produce. Work motivation was proposed by Humphreys and Einstein in 2004. For this reason, universities as academic institutions must continue to innovate, diversify their structure and look for new ways to provide their services more effectively to their customers (Jain et al., 2011).

2. The Influence of Innovative Work Behavior on Satisfaction

From the results of testing the second hypothesis, it can be concluded that there is a positive direct influence of innovative work behavior on satisfaction with a path coefficient value of 0.484. This means that innovative work behavior has a direct positive effect on satisfaction. The results of this research are in line with the opinions of several experts, including Asurakkody and Kim, who said that lecturers' innovative work behavior in carrying out their work can influence the level of satisfaction of students as customers. Innovative work behavior generally refers to the process of creating, using new tools or applications in carrying out their work, both directly and indirectly, can improve the quality of the results of the learning process carried out by lecturers in class (Asurakkody & Kim, 2020).

A professional lecturer is required to meet various requirements including formal educational qualifications, profession, scientific competence, ability to communicate, have a creative and productive spirit, have a high work ethic and commitment to his profession and always carry out continuous self-development along with developments in science. And technology. In practice, every lecturer or institution or campus has various kinds of obstacles and limitations, therefore innovative work behavior is needed by lecturers in carrying out all their work to cover all limitations. In the context of organizational behavior, this problem is often faced by lecturers because of the demands of their profession. In times like the Covid-19 pandemic, all lecturers are required to give their best with all their limitations. Still some lecturers in teaching do not show innovative work behavior, including the teaching methods of some lecturers are still conventional, there is no sharing of knowledge about appropriate learning methods.

Lecturers who have innovative work behavior will always have new things to give to students, so that students always look forward to their presence. Students always eagerly await the next meeting with the lecturer concerned. In such a position, innovative lecturers are used as central figures by students in terms of interest and enthusiasm for learning, especially in terms of the courses taught by the lecturer. For this reason, Banten Maritime Science Polytechnic lecturers must have the ability so that they have more value in the sense of being more capable, more skilled and more qualified so that they can be optimally efficient.

To improve lecturers' innovative work behavior, it is necessary to pay attention to the quality work life (QWL) factor. Quality of work life (QWL) refers to whether a person's work environment is pleasant or unpleasant. The main goal is the development of an excellent work environment. The main focus of Quality of Work Life itself is that the work environment and all work within it must be compatible with people and technology. In educational institutions such as the Banten Maritime Science Polytechnic, one of the ways to increase lecturers'

innovative work behavior is by improving the quality of work life (QWL), because in this way lecturers will feel at home and comfortable at work. All needs, both material and psychological, can be met.

3. The Influence of Work Motivation on Innovative Work Behavior

From the results of testing the third hypothesis, it can be concluded that there is a positive direct influence of work motivation on innovative work behavior with a path coefficient value of 0.649. This means that work motivation has a direct positive effect on innovative work behavior.

Work motivation is encouragement from within the lecturer or stimulation from outside the lecturer that makes the lecturer willing to move to carry out an activity or job optimally with all that he has. Motivation has a role in forming employees' innovative work behavior, this is because to innovate requires more encouragement than usual work. There are many ways that organizations can do to improve the abilities of their employees, including holding workshops, training, seminars and many others (Ibrahim et al., 2017). There is one thing that leaders sometimes forget in order to increase innovative work behavior, namely encouraging employee motivation to work better by loving their work, and continuously making improvements on an ongoing basis and ultimately this will be reflected in the innovative work behavior of the lecturers at work.

Intrinsic encouragement originating from within employees has been proven to increase employees' innovative work behavior (Ngan, 2015). This proves that to make a change or increase innovative work behavior, encouragement is needed from within (work motivation). Innovative work behavior will emerge from within a person when employees have the drive or motivation to work better (Scott & Bruce, 1994), a similar thing was expressed in Bos-Nehles et.al's research which said that employee motivation can generate good ideas. Innovative in work (Bos-Nehles & Veenendaal, 2017). Newstrom further explained that employee motivation has an influence in forming employee innovative work behavior. Work motivation is an internal and external force that causes employees to be willing to do their work effectively and efficiently in faster ways and this behavior is reflected in employee work behavior. Innovative (Newstrom, 2014).

Bateman and Snell also say that work motivation refers to employee strength that arises either from within or outside the employee which encourages employees to complete their work and is reflected in innovative employee work behavior in completing their tasks (Bateman & Snell, 2013). This is supported by several researches which prove that motivation is one of the main elements in achieving output results. An important aspect of motivation is how people perceive that certain work behaviors will be rewarded and how fair or equitable the rewards are. Two well-known motivational theories that focus on trust are expectancy theory and justice theory (Gomez-Mejia & Balkin, 2012).

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of theoretical and empirical studies that researchers studied regarding work motivation variables, innovative work behavior on cadet satisfaction can be concluded as follows:

1. Work motivation has a direct effect on cadet satisfaction, meaning that the strength, initiative and perseverance of lecturers in carrying out the TriDharma of Higher Education has a 38% effect on cadet satisfaction in learning.
2. Innovative work behavior has a direct influence on cadet satisfaction, meaning that the application of lecturer creativity during the pandemic by developing ideas and making breakthroughs in implementing new ideas at work has a very big influence on cadet satisfaction by 48%.
3. Work motivation has a direct effect on innovative work behavior. This means that strength, initiative and intensity have very dominant factors, namely 64% in the formation of lecturers' innovative work behavior attitudes. It's crucial to be honest about the study's caveats. Limitations in drawing conclusions about causation stem from the inherently correlational nature of cross-sectional studies and the potential for response biases in self-report measures. Longitudinal or experimental studies in the future that use objective measurements of digital distractions might give more convincing evidence of a causal association between mindfulness and digital distractions.

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